

Recollections from the current head of teaching at the Department of Electronic and Electrical Engineering at UCL on Nina Thornhill's Legacy

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Abstract: Sally Day is professor of photonics as the Department of Electronic and Electrical Engineering at University College London, which she joined in 1992, eight years after Nina. She is the current head of teaching. Like Nina Sally studied at Oxford University and both share a passion for education. Here she recollects the impact Nina's work had on teaching and education at the UCL department.

Keywords: University College London, head of teaching, female academics, Krakow.

My first, effectively a virtual, meeting with Nina, was my occupancy of her office when I first arrived at UCL as a Royal Society University Research Fellow in 1992. She was away on sabbatical and so I got to use her well-appointed office on the 8th floor of the Roberts building, until an office became available on the 11th floor and she returned.

Over the years it was clear that Nina was a popular, dedicated and thorough lecturer. She was generous with her time, not just to students, but also to new lecturers and it was a delight to observe one of her lectures once and see the logical, clear explanations that she gave to students.

She inspired me, many years later, to become the Head of Teaching, having seen the way that she developed the teaching in the department, with students at the centre of her thinking, but with an engineer's view of making sure that we had a system that worked within the constraints. It was a loss

to the department when she decided to leave to another London institution, but the opportunity to set up the lab at Imperial was clearly not to be missed.

For a few years Electronic Engineering at UCL could be proud to have four female academics (out of about 25 or 30), which in the 90's was probably reasonably unusual. It's taken a while to improve on that, but I think that one of Nina's legacies was that Polina (Bayvel) and I could follow from Nina's quiet, confident example that she definitely belonged in the department.

It was typical of Nina that when I happened to see her on the street in Krakow where I was on holiday last summer and where she has been taking (another?) sabbatical, that she was quick to arrange to meet for lunch and that we could chat as though no time had passed since we were first colleagues over 25 years ago.